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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

DINIY-MA'RIFIY QISSALARDA TARIXIY SHAXSLAR TALQINI

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Alisher Navoiyning “Tarixi anbiyo va hukamo” asari bashariyatni iymone'tiqodga da'vat etuvchi, o'zlarining hamida axloqi, yuksak insoniy fazilatlar bilan kishilarga o'rnak bo'luvchi, hayratomuz mo'jizalari bilan Allohning bir-u borligi, yagonaligiga iymon keltirishga undovchi payg'ambarlar va ilm-u hikmat sohibi bo'lgan donishmand – faylasuflar hayotining ibratli lavhalari, hikmatli so'zlaridan tarkib topgan.

Demak, “Tarixi anbiyo va hukamo” asari avliyo va anbiyolar, olimlar, hukamolar tarixiga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, asarda payg'ambarlarning ahli ayoli, farzandlari, kasbi kori haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Shu tariqa muallif Odam atodan boshlab o'tgan payg'ambar va valilardan 59 tasining hayoti, tarjimai holini batafsil yoritadi. 4 ta obid hamda 13 hukamo haqida fikr yuritadi va ularning hikmatli so'zlaridan namuna keltiradi.

Asarning muhim xususiyatlarning yana biri insonning yo'l qo'ygan xatolariga munosabati masalasidir. Navoiy xato qilgan kishini qattiq qoralamaydi. Hamma ham, hatto payg'ambarlar ham xato qilishi mumkin. Ammo, xatoni tushunib, to'g'ri yo'lga tushib olgan odamgina saodatlidir, - deydi Alisher Navoiy. Bunga Muso, Yusuf, Dovud, Sulaymon kabi payg'ambarlarning xatoga yo'l qo'yishi va uni tushunib, tezda tavba-tazarruga tushishlari yorqin guvohdir.

“Tarixi anbiyo va hukamoning ikkinchi qismi “Hukamo zikri” deb nomlangan bo'lib, unda bashariyat tarixida katta nufuzga ega bo'lgan olimlar va faylasuflar haqida ixcham tasvir va ma'lumotlar beriladi, ularning hikmatli so'zlaridan namunalar keltiriladi. “Hukamo zikri”ning eng muhim fazilati shundaki, shoir o'sha faylasuflar tomonidan aytilgan purma'no fikrlarning asl mohiyatini bir bayt she'rdan umumlashtiradi. Baytlar nihoyatda ta'sirchanligi va xotirada oson muhrlanishi bilan ahamiyatlidir.

“Tarixi anbiyo va hukamo asari” Alisher Navoiyning payg'ambarlar va olimlar haqida nihoyatda chuqur bilimga ega ekanligini namoyish etadi. Ulug' mutafakkir bu sohadagi bilimlarini bayon etish bilan, o'tgan buyuk siymolar haqida hikoya qilish, ularning hikmatomuz so'zlarini keltirish bilan yoshlarni komil inson bo'lib yetishuvlari lozimligini uqtirganday bo'ladi. Shunisi diqqatga sazovorki, asarda tilga olingan shaxslar – payg'ambarlar ham, hakim-faylasuflar ham Sharq va G'arbgga mansub ulug' siymolardir. Demak, Alisher Navoiy asarda umuminsoniy qadriyatlar haqida so'zlaydi va ulardan bahramand bo'lishga da'vat etadi.

Hazrat Navoiy “Tarixi anbiyo va hukamo” asarida ko'plab tarixiy voqea-hodisalarga, tarixiy shaxslarga murojaat qilgan. Shu sababli bu asar tarix ilmida ham muhim manba sifatida o'rganiladi. Shoirning tarixnavislik mahorati hakimlar bobida

yaqqol ko‘zga tashlanib, turadi. Navoiy ular haqida qisqa va lo‘nda ma‘lumot beradi: *“Aristotolis hakim Aflotunning shogirdidir, Iskandarning vaziri erdi. Aning so‘zlaridan budurkim, podshoh ulug‘ rudg‘a o‘xshar va atbo‘i arig‘larg‘akim, ul ruddin ayrildilarkim, ul rud suyig‘a har hol bo‘lsa, arig‘larg‘a hamul holdur. Ul chuchuk bo‘lsa, bular chuchuk; ul achig‘ bo‘lsa, bular achig‘; ul sof bo‘lsa, bular sof; ul loy bo‘lsa, bular loy. Bas podshohg‘a vojibdur – g‘oyat hikmat va e‘tidodol bilan maosh qilmoq, to xayl va hashami anga mutobaat qilgaylar.*

Shoh daryo va xalq anhor,

Ikisining suyig‘a bir maza bor”¹¹.

Parchadan ma‘lum bo‘lib turibdiki, Aristotel Aflotunning shogirdi bo‘lib, Iskandarning vaziri. Alisher Navoiy Iskandar nomini payg‘ambarlar qismida ham tilga oladi, ammo Zulqarnayn (Iskandarning laqabi, aynan; ikki shox egasi¹²) deb ishlatadi. Hakimlar qismida esa bu so‘z qo‘shib ishlatilmaydi. Biz bundan tarixda Iskandar nomli ikki kishi bo‘lgan ekan deb, shoshilinch qaror chiqarmasligimiz lozim, chunki Aleksandr Makedonskiyning laqabi “Zulqarnayn” ekanligi boshqa bir necha manbalarda ham tilga olingan. Navoiyning o‘zi ham “Tarixi muluki Ajam” kitobida bu haqda batafsil ma‘lumot bergan va Iskandar Ya‘juj-Ma‘jujlardan himoyalani uchun devor qurdirgani haqida aytib o‘tgan. Bundan tashqari, ushbu asarda *“Banokatiyda va “Devon un-nasab” kitobidin mundoq naql qilibdurlarkim, Iskandar Xurmus Rumiy o‘g‘lidurkim, Xurmus oatsi Lafti binni Yunon binni Torax binni Yofas binni Nuhdur”¹³.* deb qayd etadi. Demak, kelib chiqishi jihatidan Iskandar Nuh (a.s.)ning o‘g‘li Yofas (s.a.) avlodiga borib taqaladi.

Yuqoridagilardan ma‘lum bo‘ladiki, Navoiyning “Tarixi anbiyo va hukamo” asari tarixshunoslik ilmida ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Shoir har bir hakim haqida so‘z yuritganda uning ustozini kim ekanligini aytadi va ustoz-shogirdlik tizimida ularning qatorini izchillik bilan davom ettirib boradi.

Alisher Navoiy islom dinining mohiyatan insonsevar, komil inson va komil insoniy jamiyat tarbiyasiga xizmat qiluvchi ilm ekanligi uchun ham o‘zining barcha qiziqishlari kalitini undan izladi. Navoiy tasavvufiy dunyoqarashining falsafiy zaminini tashkil etuvchi vujuduyun (panteizm) ta‘limotida ta‘kidlanganidek, Alloh taoloning husn-u jamoli, kuch-qudrati va hikmati biz ko‘rib, idrok etayotgan olamda yoyilgandir, deb tushundi.

Umuman olganda, “Tarixi anbiyo va hukamo”ning har ikkala faslida ham insoniyat tarixida evrilish paydo etgan buyuklarning hayoti, hikmatli so‘zlaridan ibrat olishga da‘vat etiladi, insonning komillik rutbasini qozonishi uchun asos bo‘lgan umuminsoniy qadriyatlar haqida fikr yuritiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

¹¹ Alisher Navoiy. To‘la asarlar to‘plami. 10 jildlik. – Toshkent: G‘.G‘ulom nomidagi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, 2011. 8-jild., 601-bet.

¹² Navoiy asarlari lug‘ati. T.: G‘.G‘ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san‘at nashriyoti. 1972 yil, 259-bet.

¹³ Alisher Navoiy. To‘la asarlar to‘plami. 10 jildlik. – Toshkent: G‘.G‘ulom nomidagi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, 2011 yil. 8-jild. 618-bet.

1. Alisher Navoiy. To‘la asarlar to‘plami. 10 jildlik. – Toshkent: G‘.G‘ulom nomidagi nashriyot-matbaa ijodiy uyi, 2011. 8-jild,, 601-bet. 618-bet.
2. Navoiy asarlari lug‘ati. T.: G‘.G‘ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san‘at nashriyoti. 1972 yil, 259-bet.